

ENERGY EFFICIENT FULL ADDER CELL DESIGN WITH USING CARBON NANOTUBE FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTORS IN 32 NANOMETER TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Full Adder is one of the critical parts of logical and arithmetic units. So, presenting a low power full adder cell reduces the power consumption of the entire circuit. Also, using Nano-scale transistors, because of their unique characteristics will save energy consumption and decrease the chip area. In this paper we presented a low power full adder cell by using carbon nanotube field effect transistors (CNTFETs). Simulation results were carried out using HSPICE based on the CNTFET model in 32 nanometer technology in Different values of temperature and VDD.

KEYWORDS

Low power circuit; Carbon Nanotube Filed Effect Transistors; Nano Transistors; Full Adder

1. INTRODUCTION

Full adder cells are one of the most important parts of the arithmetic operations [1]. So, using an optimized full adder cell increase the performance of these operations. So, designing faster and low-power FAs was the driving force behind many results reported during the last decade. The main purpose of such designs has create faster FAs while also reducing their power consumption.

In this paper we present a low power full adder cell.

Moore believes that the number of transistors on a chip will be double about every two year [2]. To achieve this aim, we have to reduce the size of the transistor into Nano-scale region [3-4]. Due to the limitations of silicon based Field Effect Transistors (FETs) we need to use an efficient alternative technology.

Carbon Nanotube Field Effect Transistor (CNTFET) is an optimized alternative for the conventional CMOS technology [4].

This paper organize as follows:

In section 2, we review the carbon nanotube field effect transistors (CNTFETs) and their Specifications, The previous designs of full adders discuss in section 3 and then present our

proposed design in section 4 and finally, simulation results in section 5. Conclusion will present in Section 6.

2. CNTFETs

Carbon Nano Tubes (CNTs) are cylindrical shape of graphite sheets that rolled as tube [5]. The carbon nanotubes have chirality vector (m, n) that depend on values of them and either they can be metallic or semiconducting [6-7].

Carbon nanotube field effect transistors (CNTFETs) are a kind of transistors that use carbon nanotubes as their channel. There are two form of CNTFET: Schottky Barrier CNTFET (SB-CNTFET) and MOSFET-like CNTFET. In MOSFET-like source and drain are made of doped carbon nanotubes and the intrinsic semiconducting carbon nanotubes are used in the channel region. The channel in the Schottky barrier (SB) CNTFET is an intrinsic semiconducting carbon nanotube and direct contacts of the metal with the semiconducting nanotubes made for source and drain regions [8-9].

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a CNTFET

CNTFETs are one of the molecular devices that avoid most fundamental silicon transistor restriction and have ballistic or near ballistic transport in their channel [10]. Therefore a semiconductor carbon nanotube is appropriate for using as channel of field effect transistors [7]. Applied voltage to the gate can be control the electrical conductance of the CNT by changing electron density in the channel.

The diameter of carbon nanotube can be expressed as equation 1 [11]:

$$(1) D_{\text{CNT}} = \frac{a \sqrt{n^2 + m^2}}{\pi}$$

The threshold voltage has reversed relationship between nanotube diameters that shows in equation 2.

$$(2) V_{TH} = \frac{0.42}{d(nm)} V$$

So, by changing the diameter of the nanotube threshold voltage can be define and also, we can define the behaviour of the transistors.

3. PREVIOUS DESIGNS

Many full adder cells have presented in the past [1, 5, 12-19]. In [1, 5, and 12] full adders were designed based on XOR/XNOR circuits. The capability of majority function encourage the designers to use this function in their designs (figure 2) [13-18]. The majority function show in equation3.

$$(3) MAJORITY(A, B, C) = AB + BC + AC = Cout$$

Figure 2. Full adder designs with majority function

Using the capacitor and resistor elements affect the power of design. In [19] the full adder cell designed without any capacitors and resistors. In this paper we present a new CNTFET full adder design with reducing the number of transistors and also we don't use any capacitor or resistor. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Full adder 4

4. NEW CNTFET FULL ADDER DESIGN

In this paper we present a full adder cell design with using carbon nanotube field effect transistors in 32 nm technology. This design implements with 24 carbon nanotube field effect transistors (CNTFETs) and due to the implementation of this circuit in Nano-scale, the power of this design is better than the CMOS one. Also this circuit implemented by reducing the number of transistors in comparison with the previous CNTFET designs. This factor is also optimizes power supply of the circuit. This design implements based on equation 4. Schematic of this circuit design shows in figure 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Cout} &= AB + BC + AC \\
 \text{SUM} &= ABC + \overline{ABC} + \overline{ABC} + \overline{ABC} \\
 (4) \quad &= ABC + A(\overline{AB} + \overline{AC} + \overline{BC}) + B(\overline{AB} + \overline{AC} + \overline{BC}) + C(\overline{AB} + \overline{AC} + \overline{BC}) \\
 &= ABC + A(\overline{AB + AC + BC}) + B(\overline{AB + AC + BC}) + C(\overline{AB + AC + BC}) \\
 &= ABC + A(\overline{\text{Cout}}) + B(\overline{\text{Cout}}) + C(\overline{\text{Cout}})
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4. New CNTFET Full adder design

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation results show in tables 1-3. These Simulation results were carried out using HSPICE based on the CNTFET model in 32 nanometer technology. Tables1-3 show the Power, Delay and PDP results in Different values of temperature and VDD. As shown in table1 and 3, the Power and Power-Delay Product (PDP) of the circuit have increased by growing the VDD but it has not appreciably changes by growing the temperature (figure 5-6). The Delay parameter has decreases by increasing the VDD (as shown in table 2).

Table 1: Power consumption results for various amounts of VDD and Temperature (*10-9)

V _{DD} \Temp °C	0	9	18	27	36	45	54
0.7	2.6936	2.6913	2.7776	2.6864	2.72	2.6759	2.6842
0.8	3.8247	3.7974	3.7915	3.8371	3.8419	3.8521	3.8769
0.9	5.8277	5.834	5.8614	5.9341	5.842	5.9107	5.8542
1	8.5178	8.5429	8.5635	8.6274	8.9283	8.6518	8.6511
1.1	12.505	12.266	12.264	12.313	12.927	12.26	12.565
1.2	18.692	19.459	18.808	18.326	18.504	19.466	18.645

Table 2: Delay results for various amounts of VDD and Temperature(*10-10)

V _{DD} \Temp °C	0	9	18	27	36	45	54
0.7	1.3229	1.3186	1.3138	1.3077	1.3032	1.2981	1.2944
0.8	1.2403	1.2342	1.2301	1.2258	1.2208	1.2175	1.2132
0.9	1.2004	1.1961	1.1938	1.1898	1.1851	1.1802	1.1775
1	1.1385	1.134	1.1298	1.1235	1.1187	1.1142	1.1101
1.1	1.1119	1.1087	1.1021	1.0969	1.0917	1.0892	1.0855
1.2	1.0921	1.0891	1.083	1.0788	1.0735	1.0701	1.0671

Table 3: PDP results for various amounts of VDD and Temperature(*10-19)

V _{DD} \Temp °C	0	9	18	27	36	45	54
0.7	3.5634	3.5487	3.6492	3.5130	3.5447	3.4736	3.4744
0.8	4.7438	4.6868	4.6639	4.7035	4.6902	4.6899	4.7035
0.9	6.9956	6.9780	6.9973	7.0604	6.9234	6.9758	6.8933
1.0	9.6975	9.6876	9.6750	9.6929	9.9881	9.6398	9.6036
1.1	13.9043	13.5993	13.5162	13.5061	14.1124	13.3536	13.6393
1.2	20.4135	21.1928	20.3691	19.7701	19.8640	20.8306	19.8961

Figure 5. Chart of Power consumption results for various amounts of VDD and Temperature

Figure 6. Chart of PDP results for various amounts of VDD and Temperature

Finally we compare the simulation results of this Full Adder cell design with previous designs in 0.65 V VDD (Table 4).

Table4. Comparing the results with previous designs

	Power	Delay	PDP
Full adder-1[14]	5.23E-07	7.97E-11	4.17E-17
Full adder-2[16]	4.71E-07	8.82E-11	4.15E-17
Full adder-3[17]	7.12E-07	7.51E-11	5.35E-17
Full adder-4[19]	1.35E-08	3.45E-11	4.663E-19
New FA design	2.66E-09	1.30E-10	3.513E-19

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a low power full adder cell with using carbon nanotube field effect transistors. We used lower number of transistors and reduced the chip area by using these Nano-scale transistors. Results of section 5 carried out using HSPICE based on the CNTFET model in 32 nanometer technology in Different values of temperature and VDD. We compared these simulation results with previous similar works and showed that we achieve an optimized power saving.

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